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The Framework Programme for Research and Innovation

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100% Renewable Energy Supply in Buildings

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Abstract

This document describes the evaluation process and the evaluation results of the procuRE Call-off for Phase II. Three suppliers were selected to participate in Phase 2.

Revision History

Version	Date	Changes made	Authors
0.1	12.07.2022	Template and first draft	Tatiana Novikova, Nadia Koval (EMPIRICA)
0.2	10.08.2022	Evaluation input and content	Niko Natek (KSSENA)
0.3	25.08.2022	Review and additions by all partners	ALL
0.8	25.08.2022	Quality Review	Georg Vogt (EMPIRICA)
0.9	29.08.2022	Edits and addition of supplier abstracts	Niko Natek (KSSENA)
1.0.	31.08.2022	Submission	Niko Natek (KSSENA)

Statement of originality

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document reports on the conditions and the outcome of the evaluation of the call-off for Phase II. The evaluation methodology is documented in D3.1.

The work of the seven contractors during the two-month phase was evaluated by the procurers. Submission of bids for the next phase closed on 9th of July 2022, with all three contractors submitting bids for the next phase.

An evaluation committee evaluated the bids submitted using the award criteria set out in the Request for Tenders (RfT). The three highest ranked bids in terms of price and quality were selected and awarded the contract.

All contractors were informed of the outcome of the evaluation on 2nd of August 2022. The contracts were sent to the successful bidders for signature during the standstill period.

Phase II of the project started on 10th of August 2022 and will last eight months.

1 The Evaluation Process

Role of the Evaluation Committee and the Expert Board

As defined in the Request for Tenders, the evaluation of the tenders is performed by an Evaluation Committee which is assisted by an Expert Board.

The procuRE Evaluation Committee

1.1 The Evaluation Committee remained unchanged since evaluation of tenders.

The Evaluation Committee was responsible for performing the evaluation of all tenders following the procedures and according to the criteria specified in the Request for Tenders. It was chaired by the lead procurer representative, Niko Natek at KSSENA.

Each procurer nominated at least two experts to represent them in the evaluation of procurement, technical, and business issues. A total of 20 Evaluation Committee Members were nominated and accepted:

Table 1. Members of the Evaluation Committee

Procurer	Name of Evaluation Committee
KSSENA	Niko Natek
	Nejc Jurko
	Boštjan Krajnc
AMB	Marta Pascual
	Sergi Pérez
	Gil Lladó
NUREMBERG	Alexander Nordhus
	Peter Pfeifer
	Mathias Klaussner
	Thomas Schad
PORTO	João Encarnação
	Mário Rui Faria
IMM	Hasan Mancak
	Mehmet Keskin
	Yıldız Münevver Rüzgaroğlu
	Sefer Meşe
EILAT	Avi Naim
	Asaf Admon
	Elad Topel
	Dudu Zatch

The procuRE Expert Board

The procuRE Expert Board has already consulted the procuRE partners in the first phase of the project, before launching the call for tender, by informing the procuRE on technical requirements and during Phase I evaluation by providing their insights on the offers.

The Board consists of:

- Daniel Mugnier
- Diego Bertesina
- Jorge Rodrigues de Almeida
- Wim van Helden.

During the upcoming phase the focus of the board is on assessing the Renovation Packages.

Evaluation of call-off offers for Phases III

For Phases 3, neither differences in the composition of the Evaluation Committee nor in the procedure are expected apart from the fact that the evaluation will have only two steps: evaluating the offers based on the on/off and weighted award criteria.

Ensuring no conflicts of interest

Upon closing of the call for tender and drawing up the list of tenderers, the Evaluation Committee and the Expert Board members were required to sign a declaration of absence of conflict of interest. The declaration defines key commitment points.

The declarations can be found in Annex 2.

Ensuring protection of confidential information

The Evaluation Committee and the Expert Board members are also required to protect confidential data during the PCP process. The protection of confidentiality clauses is part of the declaration of absence of conflict and can be found in Annex 2 as well.

1.2 Approval of Phase I results

The evaluation process included approval of key deliverables related to the phase, and evaluation of the contractors' offers for the next phase.

Deliverables from all suppliers were considered to be successful and therefore their offers to be eligible for Phase II.

Table 2. Overview of milestones and deliverables in Phase I

Milestones	By when?	How?	Output & results
M1.1 Application of Co-Design Procedure with procurers	One month before end of phase (see Section 2.6)	Meeting and Minutes	D1.2
M1.2 All schematic designs of Renovation Packages and revised Renovation Approach	One month before end of phase (see Section 2.6)	Reports	D1.1, D1.2, Offer
Deliverables	By when?	How?	Output & results
D1.1 Renovation Approach	1 month before end of phase (see Section 2.6)	Sent by email to the Lead Procurer This deliverable is rated with the corresponding award criteria.	Improved and extended sections of the Technical Tender (sections 1.1-1.3, 2.1, 3.1).

D1.2 Renovation Packages	6 Renovation Packages, one each for all sites 1 month before end of phase (see Section 2.6)	Sent by email to the Lead Procurer and relevant procurer. This deliverable is rated as part of award criteria T2 and CF1.	One Renovation Package report per demonstration site. The structure follows from the proposal in the Renovation Approach.
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One schematic¹ Renovation Package per demonstration site is expected, each Package is to contain at least the following content. Contractors are entirely free with respect to format, presentation and process of generating the Renovation Packages.

- An Executive Summary including explanatory graphics of no more than two pages understandable by non-experts.*
- **Schematic Design level drawings** (plans and schematics) **sufficient to evaluate viability** of all technical systems (mechanical, electric, monitoring and control, architectural and structural, if subject of the Renovation Package)*
- The list and description of materials and components used for the retrofit, the guarantees and certifications on the materials and related aftersales services intended to be provided. Solutions must be included for heating & cooling which ensures hygrothermal comfort and air quality (Indoor Environment Quality - IEQ) inside the structures*
- The description of the systems for metering, measurement, control of energy flows and the identification of faults inside the buildings, allowing for monitoring and verification of performance, as well as easy access for operators*
- Preliminary installation work plan, including procedures for dealing with old materials, installation of new systems and with indicative Gantt charts of the activities.*
- Preliminary ordinary and extraordinary maintenance plans, including i) assignment of responsibilities and description of intervention flows, ii) intervention times after notification of failures, iii) maintenance status and useful life of the materials installed at the end of the (service) contract.*
- Assessment of the Renovation Package energy, environmental and IEQ performance, including at least on the KPIs specified in the Challenge Brief section 1.2 and reported following the format defined in the Technical Tender Application Template (TD6)*
- Economic plan including structure of contracts for energy and system-relevant facility management services, clarity on ownerships and responsibilities and a clear and concise summary of all costs for procurers per year of operation (e.g. annual fees, design, investment, operation and maintenance costs), including the use of incentives, contracting schemes and financing models as well as uncomplicated rule set for discretions from performance benchmark / KPIs induced by either party (see Challenge Brief section 2.1)**
- Annex with results from building audit, surveys, site visit.

* Evaluated as part of award sub-criterion T2; ** Evaluated as part of CF1

D1.3 Report on Co-Design Procedure with procurers	1 month before end of phase (see Section 2.6)	Sent by email to the Lead Procurer and relevant procurer.	Documentation (minutes, actions etc.) of Co-Design procedure. The progress is expected to influence D1.2.
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¹ The term is not universally defined. The following is to be considered an indication: Schematic design is a rough construction drawing that offers a general overview of a project's basic features and construction cost estimates, allowing the team to determine if a concept fits within the project budget, is compliant and fits regulations. With schematic designs, the team turns ideas into physical for further editing to help craft the construction project and prepare the team for the next phase of the architectural plan. Schematic design is the first phase of the architectural design process, which includes design development, construction documents, bidding, and construction administration.

			Lessons learnt are expected to be incorporated in D1.1.
D1.4a Project abstract	Start of Phase (see Section 2.6)	In the format required by the EU for publication Sent by email to the Lead Procurer	Written report (template will be provided)
D1.4b End of phase report	End of phase (see Section 2.6)	In the format required by the EU for publication Sent by email to the Lead Procurer	Written report (template will be provided)

Each end-of-phase report shall contain:

- a project abstract (in the format required by the EU for publication) to be published on the website.
- a summary of the main results achieved by each contractor and conclusions from the phase (in the format required by the EU for publication)
- a description of any Results generated
- a section that explains the measures taken by the contractor to protect the Results (IPR)
- a declaration of the resources expended, broken down as in the offer. Due evidence of the resources deployed shall be appended to the report.
- a list of names and location of personnel that carried out the R&D activities and a declaration that at least 50% of the work was carried out within the EU27 or a country associated to Horizon 2020

Payments based on satisfactory completion of milestones and deliverables of the phase

Payments corresponding to each PCP phase **will be subject to the *satisfactory completion*** of the deliverables and milestones for that phase.

Satisfactory completion will be assessed by the Evaluation Committee composed of representatives of the Buyers Group.

Satisfactory completion will be assessed according to the following requirements:

- if the work corresponding to that milestone / deliverable has been carried out
- if a reasonable minimum quality has been delivered
- if the reports have been submitted on time
- if the monies have been allocated to the planned objectives
- if the monies have been allocated and the work has been carried out according to the on/off criteria (place of performance, public funding and R&D definition criteria), and
- if the work has been carried out in compliance with the provisions of the contract (including in particular verification if the contractor has duly protected and managed IPRs generated in the respective phase).

‘Reasonable minimum quality’ of a report means that:

- the report can be read by somebody who is familiar with the topic, but not an expert
- the report gives insight in the tasks performed in and the results
- the report uses any reasonable template or form provided to the tenderer.

‘Reasonable minimum quality’ of a demonstration (for Phase II or III) means:

- the demonstration can be understood by somebody who is familiar with the topic, but not an expert (for instance, somebody with operational but not technical knowledge)
- the demonstration shows how the innovation works, how it can be used and (if applicable) how it is operated and maintained

- the demonstration is accessible to parties appointed by the procurers, unless these are direct competitors of the contractor.

Satisfactory completion in each of the phases does not mean successful completion. (A PCP could, for instance, be satisfactorily completed even if it concludes that the innovation is not feasible.)

Eligibility for the next phase based on successful completion of the phase

Eligibility for participation in the next phase **will be subject to *successful completion*** of the current phase.

Successful completion of a phase will be assessed by the assessment committee against the following requirements:

- if all milestones have been successfully completed
- if the R&D results meet the minimum functionality/performance requirements of the challenge description (i.e. the minimum quality/efficiency improvements which the procurers set forth for the innovative solutions to achieve)
- if the results of the R&D are considered to be promising.

‘Promising’ means:

- for Phase I, that the feasibility is convincing
- for Phase II, that the feasibility, the applicability in an operational setting and the potential impact of the product is convincing.

Opening of tenders

1.3

The Lead Procurer opened the tenders electronically on 12 of July 2022 at 09:00 local time (CET).

Technical and administrative forms and were shared with the Buyers Group and all partners.

1.4

Evaluation process

For a detailed description of the process, please see D3.1 or the Request for Tender D2.1 TD1.

Exclusion criteria

No changes to supplier consortia occurred.

Selection criteria

No changes to supplier consortia occurred.

Compliance criteria

No changes to supplier consortia occurred.

Award criteria

On/off award criteria

No changes to supplier consortia occurred.

Weighted award criteria

The weights and maximum points for each criterion for Phase II.

Table 3. Overview of weighted award criteria (Phase II)

Weighted award criteria	Maximum points	Threshold	Weight
Technical Criterion			60%
T1 - System Integration: Methodology and Process	35	15	
T2 - Degree of achievement of objectives in reference buildings	30	20	
T3 - Training & Education of professionals and users	15	10	
T4 - Innovativeness compared to market state-of-the-art	20	10	
Total for technical	100	50	
Commercial Feasibility Criterion			15%
CF1 - Investment, energy service contracting and financing models / Total cost of ownership	65	40	
CF2 - Commercialisation Plan	35	20	
Total for commercial feasibility	100	60	
Project Management Criterion			25%
PM1- Interface to procurers	30	15	
PM2 - Quality and completeness of the work-plan as well as detail of task and result descriptions	35	20	
PM3 - Feasibility of plan and resources to meet the objectives	35	20	
Total for project management	100	60	
Overall total score for tender	100	50	

The Evaluation Committee Members awarded points per criterion based on the following assessment table:

Table 4. procuRE assessment scheme

Assessment	Description	Score
Outstanding	The response exceeds the requirement providing significant added value to it, which is described very convincingly.	10
Excellent	The response fully meets the requirement and the provided explanation is very convincing.	9
Very good	The response addresses the requirement very well, but a small number of inconsistencies, or minor shortcomings are present.	8

Good	The response addresses well the requirement in most respects and provides certain information which is relevant, but a small number of shortcomings are present.	7
Fairly good	The response meets the requirement in certain material respects and provides certain information, which is relevant, but which is lacking or inconsistent in material respects, or a number of shortcomings are present.	6
Fair	The response addresses multiple aspects of the requirement, but the provided explanation is not fully convincing, and a number of shortcomings are present.	5
Poor	The response broadly addresses the requirement, but there are multiple shortcomings.	4
Fairly poor	The response inadequately addresses the requirement, or it contains significant shortcomings.	3
Very poor	The response significantly fails to meet the requirements, or it contains serious shortcomings.	2
Extremely poor	Multiple important aspects of the requirement are missing.	1
Unacceptable	No response is provided, or none of the aspects of the requirement are met.	0

The Committee decided on the final award criteria scoring in an online meeting by a simple majority vote.

Points achieved for each criterion are calculated based on the on the score, the formula can be summarised as: score (as defined in Table 4 * max points (see Table 3) / max score (10 from Table 4). For detail see Request for Tender TD1.

- 1.5 Tenders were required to score above the thresholds given in the award criteria (see Table 3), for each threshold. Tenders that did not reach the minimum quality thresholds were rejected.

Ranking of tenders

The price-quality ranking was created for all offers passing above process.

The contract was awarded to the most economically advantageous tender, i.e. the tender scoring above all thresholds and offering the best price-quality ratio determined in accordance with the formula below. The price applied consisted of the total offered price relating to the next specific contract (contract for each phase) in the PCP.

A weight of 80/20 is given to quality and price, respectively.

$$Total\ Score_{Tender\ i} = 80\% * Quality_{Tender\ i} + 20\% * \left(\frac{lowest\ price\ of\ all\ tenders}{Price_{Tender\ i}} * 100 \right)$$

After applying the formula, at least the highest six ranking tenders were to be awarded the contract.

In the call-offs for Phases III, further sub-criteria may be added and the maximum point distribution adjusted. These serve to fine-tune the award criteria and take into account improved information relevant to addressing the challenge without significantly changing the criteria presented here.

Award decision and notification

Tenderers were informed via E-Mail of the outcome of their proposal and, if applicable, the next steps. The outcome letter contained the justification of the evaluation result.

Payments for Phase I

1.6 Payments are conditional on the acceptance of deliverables shown in section 1.2 by the Buyers Group. All three contractors involved in Phase I submitted their deliverables on time, which were rated satisfactory by all procurers. Invoicing is currently in progress.

1.7 Since the budget in Phase I was not fully used, it is expected that **€719,913** from the PCP budget of Phase I were transferred to Phase II. The large sum is result of the fact that of all offers submitted during the tender only three offers were eligible or of sufficient quality to be funded.

Evaluation time schedule

1.8 The evaluation was planned to be performed in the period 12 July– 30 July 2022. The evaluation was performed as planned, and the outcome communicated to the tenderers on 02 August 2022.

Table 5: procuRE tender evaluation timeline

Date	Activity
10.05.2022	Start of Phase I
11.07.2022	Submission of offer for next phase
12.07.2022	Opening of Tenders
02.08.2022	Tenderers notified of the outcome of the evaluation
05.08.2022	Contractual details sent to selected tenderers for Phase II
19.08.2022	Evaluation comments and scores per sub-criterion were submitted to tenderers
26.08.2022	Deadline for receipt of signed contracts
31.08.2022	Date of signature by Lead Procurer

2 Evaluation results and abstracts of winning tenders

Three submissions were received.

Award criteria – results

Three tenders were evaluated on award criteria. The aggregated results are summarised below.

Table 6. Evaluation results and ranking of tenders

ID	Name of Tender	Rank	Price-Quality Score	Quality Score	Technical	Commercial Feasibility	Project Management
T002	Defcon8	1	73	67	66	67	67
T001	SENER	2	73	70	68	73	72
T005	R2M	3	69	70	70	69	70

Out of the three tenders evaluated on the award criteria:

- All three met the minimum score thresholds
- All three proceeded to being evaluated by applying the price-quality formula after being

Abstracts of winning tenders

Abstracts in order of ranking. The abstracts are taken from the PCP Phase 2 deliverable D2.7a provided in the annex.

2.2.1 SEBR – Defcon8 – T002

“Smart Energy Building Renovation (SEBR) is a Consortia of several companies that transforms old buildings into energy wise efficient buildings with state-of-the-art technology. From envelope, HVAC, PV, batteries, water management, to real time Energy Monitoring Systems, interior air quality and car chargers... we cover your needs and expectations.

It's not a one size fits all solution. The final design is tailored to each buildings' needs conserving scalability, modularity & flexibility.

Savings depend much on users' engagement. That's why we provide training for end users and Facility Managers. We explain to end users what's been done in the building and how to best profit from it. We provide a list of saving tips on energy & water usage. User friendly understandable information for all ages & backgrounds.

Facility managers receive technical training. How to interpret data & graphs correctly and generate useful reports.

Following circular economy principles, we try to use local materials whenever possible, to minimize transport costs and CO2 emissions.

AWARENESS FOSTERS SAVINGS”

2.2.2 CLARITY – SENER – T001

“Clarity proposal is a unique platform which will deliver 100% RES in 3 steps:

- Maximizing the % of RES energy generation, considering the weather climate and technical conditions.
- Studying financial and economic viability of the RES Package,
- Operational Management based on IA software to reduce costs and maximise the demand of the % of RES.

The proposal is a unique platform which will optimise this approach to a 100% RES scenario but also a dynamic operational system which help maximizing that scenario. The platform can be used by owners and procurers without any level of expertise.

The goal of the optimisation is to evaluate the optimal on-site renewable energy technologies to be installed in the building according to the combination of economic, regulatory, technical, environmental impacts and operational management and determine the optimal sizing of them based on the building's conditions.”

2.2.3 PARidSE– R2M – T005

PARadISE addresses the challenge of maximising the share of renewables used in existing buildings, while smoothing the integration of necessary system components, optimising the user's comfort and facilitating O&M. For that, PARadISE aims to provide a toolkit composed of reliable and modular hardware and software technologies while helping procurers make informed decisions based on a framework that rates technologies performance. BIM technology will be present throughout the whole process as the major enabler for the implementation of a novel retrofitting methodology. PARadISE will provide a solution that allows systematic information integration, data collection, processing, exchange and storage. In this context, PARadISE envisions a solution that serves procurers not only in the design phase, but also through the entire life-time of the retrofitting process, providing a BIM-based interface that is standardized, low intrusive, and modular. Finally, PARadISE provides procurers with all the necessary tools and education and training activities so that they can manage the solution on their own once procuRE is concluded.

2.3

Next steps

The procuRE Lead Procurer is to submit signed specific contracts to the winning tenders.

Phase 2 of the PCP began on 10th of August 2022.

Currently, suppliers are planning more frequent Co-Design meetings, participate in the consortium meeting on September 15-16th, prepare prototype testing and develop the Renovation Packages and corresponding deliverables.

Annex 1: Outcome letters sent to tenders

Notification letter T001

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Grant Agreement No. 963648.

SENER INGENIERÍA Y SISTEMAS S.A
AV. ZUGAZARTE, 56.
POSTAL CODE: 48930
GETXO (BIZKAIA, SPAIN)

Velenje, 2 August 2022

Results of the evaluation of the procuRE Call-off for Phase II

Dear Tenderer,

We are pleased to inform you that your tender has been successful in the above procurement procedure.

This letter informing you of the award of the contract does not constitute a commitment on the part of the contracting authority. Until signature of the contract by both parties, the contracting authority may cancel the procurement procedure without this entitling you to any compensation.

You will soon receive the Specific Contract for Phase II for your signature.

Should it not be possible to conclude the contract as foreseen, we reserve the right to review our decision and to award the contract to another tenderer, to cancel or abandon the procedure.

We would like to thank you for your participation in this procurement procedure.

Yours faithfully,

Boštjan Krajnc
Director
KSSENA

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Grant Agreement No. 963648.

Defcon8
Avda Corts Cat 5-7
08173 St. Cugat,
Barcelona, Spain

Velenje, 2 August 2022

Results of the evaluation of the procuRE Call-off for Phase II

Dear Tenderer,

We are pleased to inform you that your tender has been successful in the above procurement procedure.

This letter informing you of the award of the contract does not constitute a commitment on the part of the contracting authority. Until signature of the contract by both parties, the contracting authority may cancel the procurement procedure without this entitling you to any compensation.

You will soon receive the Specific Contract for Phase II for your signature.

Should it not be possible to conclude the contract as foreseen, we reserve the right to review our decision and to award the contract to another tenderer, to cancel or abandon the procedure.

We would like to thank you for your participation in this procurement procedure.

Yours faithfully,

Boštjan Krajnc
Director
KSSENA

Notification letter T005

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Grant Agreement No. 963648.

R2M Solution Spain SL
Calle Villablanca 85,
28032 Madrid
Spain

Velenje, 2 August 2022

Results of the evaluation of the procuRE Call-off for Phase II

Dear Tenderer,

We are pleased to inform you that your tender has been successful in the above procurement procedure.

This letter informing you of the award of the contract does not constitute a commitment on the part of the contracting authority. Until signature of the contract by both parties, the contracting authority may cancel the procurement procedure without this entitling you to any compensation.

You will soon receive the Specific Contract for Phase II for your signature.

Should it not be possible to conclude the contract as foreseen, we reserve the right to review our decision and to award the contract to another tenderer, to cancel or abandon the procedure.

We would like to thank you for your participation in this procurement procedure.

Yours faithfully,

Boštjan Krajnc
Director
KSSENA

Annex 2: Contractor details and Project abstracts

CLARITY– SENER – T001

Contactor Details	Type/ size of legal entity	Place of performance of contract activities	Logo
<p><u>Main contractor</u></p> <p>Sener Ingeniería y Sistemas S.A Avenida Zugazarte, 56. 48930 Las Arenas, Vizcaya, Spain Enrique Gómez Cristóbal</p> <p>Juan Ochagavía Gómez +34 629783304 juan.ochagavia@sener.es</p>	larger company	<p>% of contract value allocated to main contractor: [54] %</p> <p>% of activities for the contract performed by the main contractor in EU Member States or countries associated with Horizon 2020: [54] %</p>	
<p><u>Other consortium member</u></p> <p>FUNDACIÓ EURECAT Avda. Universitat Autònoma, 23, CP: 08290, Cerdanyola del Valles, Barcelona, Spain. Bernadette Grabenbauer Nagl +34 680771843 bernadette.grabenbauer@eurecat.org</p>	research institute	<p>% of contract value allocated to contractor [1]: [20] %</p> <p>% of activities for the contract performed by contractor [1] in EU Member States or countries associated with Horizon 2020: [20] %</p>	
<p><u>Subcontractors (if applicable)</u></p> <p>AGGITY EUROPE, S.A. c/ Frederic Mompou, 5, 08960 Sant Just Desvern, Barcelona, Spain. Javier Monjas +34 606318065 javier.monjas@aggity.com</p> <p><i>Complete as many times as there are subcontractors</i></p>	SME	<p>% of contract value allocated to subcontractor [1]: [26] %</p> <p>% of activities for the contract performed by subcontractor [1] in EU Member States or countries associated with Horizon 2020: [26] %</p>	
<p>Project abstract (+/- 1000 characters maximum)</p> <p>Clarity proposal is a unique platform which will deliver a renovation approach to reach 100% RES in 3 steps:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maximizing the % of RES energy generation and minimizing energy consumption by upgrading building facilities. • Studying financial and economic viability of the Renovation Packages. • Operational Management based on IA software to reduce costs and maximise the demand of the % of RES. <p>The proposal is a unique platform which will optimise this approach to a 100% RES scenario but also a dynamic operational system which help maximizing that scenario. The platform can be used by owners and procurers without any level of expertise.</p> <p>The goal of the optimisation is to evaluate the optimal on-site renewable energy technologies and the facilities upgrades to be installed in the building according to the combination of economic, regulatory, technical, environmental impacts and operational management and determine the optimal sizing of them based on the building's conditions.</p>			

Project funded by the EU Horizon 2020 Programme

Previous EU funding

Is the project based on / a continuation of R&D activities that were previously funded by the EU?: NO
If yes, identify this EU funding: [name EU funding programme] — [project name] — [grant number]

PARidSE– R2M – T005

Contactor Details	Type/ size of legal entity	Place of performance of contract activities	Logo
<p><u>Main contractor</u></p> <p>R2M Solution Spain SL</p> <p>Calle Villablanca 85, 28032, Madrid</p> <p>Jesús Febres</p> <p>+34 918 27 65 97</p> <p>paradise@r2msolution.com</p>	SME	<p>% of contract value allocated to main contractor: 23 %</p> <p>% of activities for the contract performed by the main contractor in EU Member States or countries associated with Horizon 2020: 100 %</p>	<p>Main contractor logo</p>
<p><u>Other consortium member(s) (if applicable)</u></p> <p>R2M Solution SRL</p> <p>Via Fratelli Cuzio, 42, Pavia 27100</p> <p>Lorenzo Cifariello</p> <p>+39 380 21 47 186</p> <p>innovativeproducts@r2msolution.com</p>	SME	<p>% of contract value allocated to contractor R2M Solution SRL: 17 %</p> <p>% of activities for the contract performed by contractor R2M Solution SRL in EU Member States or countries associated with Horizon 2020: 100 %</p>	<p>Other contractor(s) logo(s)</p>
<p>Prosume SRL</p> <p>Corso Venezia 54, Milan, 20124</p> <p>Miquel de la Mano</p> <p>+34 661 177 936</p> <p>miquel@prosume.io</p>	SME	<p>% of contract value allocated to contractor Prosume SRL: 20 %</p> <p>% of activities for the contract performed by contractor Prosume SRL in EU Member States or countries associated with Horizon 2020: 100 %</p>	
<p>ENDEF Engineering SL</p> <p>Calle P-A, 11, Ciudad de Transporte, Zaragoza, 50008</p> <p>Yolanda Lara</p> <p>+34 976 36 58 11</p> <p>yolanda.lara@endef.es</p>	SME	<p>% of contract value allocated to contractor ENDEF Engineering SL: 25 %</p> <p>% of activities for the contract performed by contractor ENDEF Engineering SL in EU Member States or countries associated with Horizon 2020: 100 %</p>	
<p>Aire Limpio 2000 S.L.</p> <p>Plaza de la Castellana 143, Planta 11, 28046 Madrid</p> <p>Vicente Pinto Madrid</p> <p>+34 914170428</p>	SME	<p>% of contract value allocated to contractor Aire Limpio 2000 S.L.: 15 %</p> <p>% of activities for the contract performed by contractor Aire Limpio 2000 S.L. in EU Member States or countries associated with Horizon 2020: 100 %</p>	

Project funded by the EU Horizon 2020 Programme

vpinto@airelimpio.com

E-mail address contact person

Project abstract (+/- 1000 characters maximum)

PARadISE addresses the challenge of maximising the share of renewables used in existing buildings, while smoothing the integration of necessary system components, optimising the user's comfort and facilitating O&M. For that, PARadISE aims to provide a toolkit composed of reliable and modular hardware and software technologies while helping procurers make informed decisions based on a framework that rates technologies performance. BIM technology will be present throughout the whole process as the major enabler for the implementation of a novel retrofitting methodology. PARadISE will provide a solution that allows systematic information integration, data collection, processing, exchange and storage. In this context, PARadISE envisions a solution that serves procurers not only in the design phase, but also through the entire life-time of the retrofitting process, providing a BIM-based interface that is standardized, low intrusive, and modular. Finally, PARadISE provides procurers with all the necessary tools and education and training activities so that they can manage the solution on their own once procuRE is concluded.

Previous EU funding

Is the project based on / a continuation of R&D activities that were previously funded by the EU?: YES/NO

If yes, identify this EU funding:

- [H2020 - NGI] - [LEDGER] - [825268]: Prosume - Data structure and protocol
- [H2020] - [LOWUP] - [723930]: Endef - Unglazed PVT
- [H2020] - [MINISTOR] - [869821]: Endef - First PVT with half-cells
- [H2020] - [HESTIA] - [957823]: R2M ES - Building modelling & MPC

Contactor Details	Type/ size of legal entity	Place of performance of contract activities	Logo
<p><u>Main contractor</u></p> <p>Defcon8 Avda Corts Catalanes 5 08º73 St.Cugat, Barcelona, Spain Name Javier Ray Phone +34 620988517 E-mail jray@defcon8.com</p>	<p>SME</p>	<p>% of contract value allocated to main contractor:21096 [5,162] %</p> <p>% of activities for the contract performed by the main contractor in EU Member States or countries associated with Horizon 2020: [100] %</p>	
<p>Name Lancey Energy Storage Address 37 rue Diderot 38000 Grenoble, France Name Olivier Guerard Phone +33(0)617479544 E-mail o.guerard@lancey.fr</p>	<p>SME</p>	<p>% of contract value allocated to contractor [74980]: [18,346] %</p> <p>% of activities for the contract performed by Lancey in EU Member States or countries associated with Horizon 2020: [100] %</p>	
<p>Name ITEC Address C/Wellington 19 08018 Barcelona Name Licinio Alfaro Phone +93 3093404 E-mail lalfaro@itec.cat</p>	<p>Non profit institute</p>	<p>% of contract value allocated to contractor [143100]: [35,014] %</p> <p>% of activities for the contract performed by ITEC in EU Member States or countries associated with Horizon 2020: [100] %</p>	
<p>Name Mondas Address Emmy Noether Str2 79110 Freiburg Name Volkmar Boerner Phone +49(0)761216089-20 Volkmar.Boerner@mondas-gmbh.de</p>	<p>SME</p>	<p>% of contract value allocated to contractor [102856]: [25,167] %</p> <p>% of activities for the contract performed by Mondas in EU Member States or countries associated with Horizon 2020: [100] %</p>	

<p>Name CIFE Address 81 rue de France 06000 Nice, FR Name Rachel Guyet Phone +33493979397 Rachel.Guyet@CIFE.eu</p>	SME	<p>% of contract value allocated to contractor [12800]: [3,132] % % of activities for the contract performed by CIFE in EU Member States or countries associated with Horizon 2020: [100] %</p>	
<p>Name 3OC Address -rue des Halles 15 75001 Paris Name Chloe Chavardes Phone +33661124367 chloe@threeoclock.co</p>	SME	<p>% of contract value allocated to contractor [38445]: [9,4] % % of activities for the contract performed by CIFE in EU Member States or countries associated with Horizon 2020: [100] %</p>	

<p>SUBCONTRACTOR Name Edison Electronics Address C/Xarol 4A Name Angel Martinez Phone +34 93 4655204 a.martinezbarbera@edison.com</p>	SME	<p>% of contract value allocated to contractor [8409]: [2,057] % % of activities for the contract performed by Edison in EU Member States or countries associated with Horizon 2020: [100] %</p>	
<p>SUBCONTRACTOR Name Anunzia Address Joanot Martorell 61 08203 Sabadell Name Marc Tallo Phone +34937259390 marc.tallo@anunzia.com</p>	SME	<p>% of contract value allocated to contractor [3500]: [0,856] % % of activities for the contract performed by Anunzia in EU Member States or countries associated with Horizon 2020: [100] %</p>	
<p>SUBCONTRACTOR Name EMC Address Campus Nord Edif C4 Jordi Girona 1-3 Name Marc Aragon Phone +34 93 4011 021 Marc.aragon@emc-barcelona.com</p>	SME	<p>% of contract value allocated to UPC [3500]: [0,856] % % of activities for the contract performed by CIFE in EU Member States or countries associated with Horizon 2020: [100] %</p>	

Project abstract (+/- 1000 characters maximum)

“Smart Energy Building Renovation (SEBR) is a Consortia of several companies that transforms old buildings into energy wise efficient buildings with state-of-the-art technology. From envelope, HVAC, PV, batteries, water management, to real time Energy Monitoring Systems, interior air quality and car chargers... we cover your needs and expectations.

It's not a one size fits all solution. The final design is tailored to each buildings' needs conserving scalability, modularity & flexibility.

Savings depend much on users' engagement. That's why we provide training for end users and Facility Managers. We explain to end users what's been done in the building and how to best profit from it. We provide a list of saving tips on energy & water usage. User friendly understandable information for all ages & backgrounds.

Facility managers receive technical training. How to interpret data & graphs correctly and generate useful reports.

Following circular economy principles, we try to use local materials whenever possible, to minimize transport costs and CO2 emissions.

AWARENESS FOSTERS SAVINGS”

Previous EU funding

Is the project based on / a continuation of R&D activities that were previously funded by the EU?: No

Annex 3: TED Contract Award Notice

[Services - 469705-2022 - TED Tenders Electronic Daily \(europa.eu\)](#)

29/08/2022 S165

- [I.](#) [II.](#) [IV.](#) [V.](#) [V.](#) [V.](#) [VI.](#)

Slovenia–Velenje: Research and experimental development services

2022/S 165–469705

Contract award notice

Results of the procurement procedure

Services

Legal Basis:

Directive 2014/24/EU

Section I: Contracting authority

I.1) Name and addresses

Official name: Energy agency of Savinjska, Šaleška and Koroška region (KSSENA)

National registration number: SI58743359

Postal address: Koroška cesta 37A

Town: Velenje

NUTS code: SI034 Savinjska

Postal code: 3320

Country: Slovenia

Contact person: Niko Natek

E-mail: suppliers@procure-pcp.eu

Telephone: +386 38961/520

Internet address(es):

Main address: www.kssena.si/en

Address of the buyer profile: www.procure-pcp.eu

I.1) Name and addresses

Official name: Àrea Metropolitana de Barcelona

National registration number: ESP0800258F

Postal address: c/62 num. 16–18, ed. B 6a planta, Zona Tranca

Town: Barcelona

NUTS code: ES511 Barcelona

Postal code: 08040

Country: Spain

Contact person: Gil Llado

E-mail: suppliers@procure-pcp.eu

Telephone: +34 932/235/151

Fax: +34 932/234/790

Internet address(es):

Main address: www.amb.cat/en/home

Address of the buyer profile: www.procure-pcp.eu

I.1)Name and addresses

Official name: Stadt Nürnberg – Hochbauamt, Kommunales Energiemanagement und Bauphysik

National registration number: DE133552578

Postal address: ZA-KEM, Marientorgraben 11

Town: Nürnberg

NUTS code: DE254 Nürnberg, Kreisfreie Stadt

Postal code: 90402

Country: Germany

Contact person: Alexander Nordhus

E-mail: suppliers@procure-pcp.eu

Telephone: +49 911/231/14584

Fax: +49 911/231/7630

Internet address(es):

Main address: www.nuernberg.de/internet/stadtportal_e

Address of the buyer profile: www.procure-pcp.eu

I.1)Name and addresses

Official name: Energaia – Energy Agency South of the Porto Metropolitan Area

National registration number: PT504454536

Postal address: Av. Manuel Violas, 476, Sala 23

Town: Vila Nova de Gaia

NUTS code: PT11A Área Metropolitana do Porto

Postal code: 4410-137

Country: Portugal

Contact person: Luís Filipe Caeiro Castanheira

E-mail: suppliers@procure-pcp.eu

Telephone: +351 22/374/72/50

Internet address(es):

Main address: www.energaia.pt/en

Address of the buyer profile: www.procure-pcp.eu

I.1)Name and addresses

Official name: Municipality of Eilat

National registration number: IL500226006

Postal address: HATIVAT HANEDEV PO Box – 14

Town: Eilat

NUTS code: IL Israel

Postal code: 88100

Country: Israel

Contact person: Assaf Admon

E-mail: suppliers@procure-pcp.eu

Telephone: +972 8/6367111

Internet address(es):

Main address: www.eilat.city/en/municipality-of

Address of the buyer profile: www.procure-pcp.eu

I.1)Name and addresses

Official name: Istanbul Metropolitan Municipality

National registration number: TR4810024824

Postal address: Osmaniye Mahallesi Cobancesme Kosuyolu Bulvari No 5 Bakirköy

Town: Istanbul

NUTS code: TR10 İstanbul

Postal code: 34568

Country: Turkey

Contact person: Ülkü Gül

E-mail: suppliers@procure-pcp.eu

Telephone: +90 2123126363/666044

Internet address(es):

Main address: www.ibb.istanbul/en

Address of the buyer profile: www.procure-pcp.eu

I.2)Information about joint procurement

The contract involves joint procurement

In the case of joint procurement involving different countries, state applicable national procurement law:

This pre-commercial procurement is carried out by KSENA who was appointed as lead procurer in the name and on behalf of the buyers group listed in I.1. The applicable national law is Slovenian.

The contract is awarded by a central purchasing body

I.4)Type of the contracting authority

Regional or local agency/office

I.5)Main activity

Other activity: Energy

Section II: Object**II.1)Scope of the procurement****II.1.1)Title:**

Pre-commercial Procurement (PCP) to buy R&D (research and development) services for Breakthrough Solutions for 100% Renewable Energy Supply in Buildings

II.1.2)Main CPV code

73100000 Research and experimental development services

II.1.3)Type of contract

Services

II.1.4)Short description:

procuRE is a PCP to buy R&D services to support cities' transition to carbon neutrality. The procurement aims to trigger new solutions to be developed and tested to address the common challenge: Achieving 100% Renewable Energy Supply in existing public buildings. Suppliers are to design, develop, and test an innovative Renovation Approach capable of generating Renovation Packages delivering 100% renewable energy supply to any existing non-residential building with adequate envelope quality. The Renovation Approach is to be tested through generating and implementing Renovation Packages for specific non-residential buildings in Buyers Group portfolios, the Demonstration Sites. More information can be found on the procuRE website: <https://procure-pcp.eu>.

II.1.6)Information about lots

This contract is divided into lots: no

II.1.7)Total value of the procurement (excluding VAT)

Value excluding VAT: 1 414 752.00 EUR

II.2)Description

II.2.2)Additional CPV code(s)

09300000 Electricity, heating, solar and nuclear energy
09310000 Electricity
09330000 Solar energy
09331000 Solar panels
09331100 Solar collectors for heat production
09331200 Solar photovoltaic modules
09332000 Solar installation
31121300 Wind-energy generators
31158100 Battery chargers
31161900 Voltage-control systems
31162000 Parts of transformers, inductors and static converters
31162100 Parts of condensers
31174000 Power supply transformers
31200000 Electricity distribution and control apparatus
31210000 Electrical apparatus for switching or protecting electrical circuits
31400000 Accumulators, primary cells and primary batteries
31440000 Batteries
31682000 Electricity supplies
32441100 Telemetry surveillance system
35125100 Sensors

38128000 Meteorology instrument accessories
38433200 Emission measurement equipment
38551000 Energy meters
39715000 Water heaters and heating for buildings; plumbing equipment
39715100 Electric instantaneous or storage water heaters and immersion heaters
39715200 Heating equipment
39715210 Central-heating equipment
39715220 Electric heating resistors
39715230 Electric soil-heating apparatus
39715240 Electric space-heating apparatus
39717200 Air-conditioning appliances
42510000 Heat-exchange units, air-conditioning and refrigerating equipment, and filtering machinery
44110000 Construction materials
44111000 Building materials
44112000 Miscellaneous building structures
44115000 Building fittings
44115800 Building internal fittings
45310000 Electrical installation work
48000000 Software package and information systems
48211000 Platform interconnectivity software package
48600000 Database and operating software package
48610000 Database systems
48611000 Database software package
48612000 Database-management system
48613000 Electronic data management (EDM)
65400000 Other sources of energy supplies and distribution
71314000 Energy and related services
71314200 Energy-management services
71314300 Energy-efficiency consultancy services
71314310 Heating engineering services for buildings
71321000 Engineering design services for mechanical and electrical installations for buildings
71321100 Construction economics services

71321200 Heating–system design services
71323100 Electrical power systems design services
71334000 Mechanical and electrical engineering services
72212190 Educational software development services
72212211 Platform interconnectivity software development services
72212931 Training software development services
72222300 Information technology services
80420000 E–learning services
71333000 Mechanical engineering services

II.2.3)Place of performance

NUTS code: DE254 Nürnberg, Kreisfreie Stadt

NUTS code: ES511 Barcelona

NUTS code: IL Israel

NUTS code: PT11A Área Metropolitana do Porto

NUTS code: SI034 Savinjska

NUTS code: TR10 İstanbul

Main site or place of performance:

Testing is expected to take place in Velenje (Slovenia); Barcelona (Spain); Nuremberg (Germany); Vila Nova de Gaia (Portugal); Istanbul (Turkey); Eilat (Israel).

II.2.4)Description of the procurement:

The procurement will take the form of a pre–commercial procurement (PCP) under which R&D service contracts will be awarded to R&D providers in parallel in a phased approach. This will make it possible to compare competing alternative solutions. Each selected operator will be awarded a framework agreement that covers three R&D phases. The three phases are: solution design, prototype development, original development and validation and testing of a limited volume of first products or services. After each phase, intermediate evaluations will be carried out to select the best of the competing solutions. The contractors with the best value–for–money solutions will be offered a specific contract for the next phase.

The selected operators will retain ownership of the intellectual property rights (IPRs) that they generate during the PCP and will be able to use them to exploit the full market potential of the developed solutions i.e. beyond the procurement. The market potential is estimated to be the majority of educational buildings (780,000) and offices (3.4 million) across Europe.

In their proposal, tenderers are requested to describe a Renovation Approach which can be applied to any school or office across the EU in response to the Challenge Brief (TD2). The Renovation Approach constitutes the set of methods, technologies, services and devices integrated in a well–documented toolkit with which suppliers tackle the 100% RES challenge in any specific building. During the project, tenderers are expected to apply their Renovation Approach in full to the Demonstration Sites. In their proposal, suppliers are to apply the relevant part of their Renovation

Approach on two hypothetical reference buildings and report on the expected resulting performance of those buildings. The proposal is rated according to the Weighted Award Criteria. In Phase I, six contractors apply their Renovation Approach and develop a specific Renovation Package for each of the six Demonstration Sites. The design level is schematic; planning and calculations are preliminary. Contractors and procurers interact via the Co-Design procedure (such a procedure must be included in the Renovation Approach) to clarify detail and decision-making. This phase aims to verify the conceptual, technological, organisational, regulatory, safety and budgetary feasibility of the solutions.

In Phase II, four contractors refine and increase the level of detail of their designs and organise tests of all user-facing ICT-systems. The design level is as detailed as possible without the requirement to constitute construction drawings. Planning and calculations should be final. The use of the Co-Design procedure should be intensified. This phase aims to turn the schematic design to detailed designs preparing all parties involved for rapid implementation; and to give future users the opportunity to test all ICT-systems.

In Phase III, two contractors implement their Renovation Packages at the three Demonstration Sites allocated to them. Designs are turned into construction drawings, the solutions are installed, made operational, maintained and performance data collected. Contractors and procurers interact via the Continuous Commissioning procedure (this must be included in the Renovation Approach) and demonstrate how O&M and contracting plays out in real-life. This phase serves to verify both the prototype Renovation Packages and the whole prototype Renovation Approach.

After the end of the project, it is the intent of procurers to continue the operation of the solutions at all Demonstrations Sites. To enable this, contractors will submit performance and O&M offers during Phase III based on the Renovation Package submitted. There is the possibility of a follow-up project (PPI) to ensure solutions can be scaled up depending on project success and whether service prices are, at this point, commercially competitive or require further support.

II.2.5) Award criteria

Quality criterion – Name: Quality / Weighting: 80

Price – Weighting: 20

II.2.11) Information about options

Options: no

II.2.13) Information about European Union funds

The procurement is related to a project and/or programme financed by European Union funds: yes

Identification of the project:

This procurement receives funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme, under Grant Agreement No 963648– procuRE (<https://procure-pcp.eu>).

The EU has given a grant for this procurement but is not participating as a contracting authority in the procurement.

II.2.14) Additional information

procuRE carried out a series of open market consultation (OMC) events in the period 22 April 2021 – 9 July 2021 to inform the specifications of the tender. All materials and recording are available at <https://procure-pcp.eu>. Participation in the OMC events is not a prerequisite for submitting a tender for this call.

Section IV: Procedure

IV.1)Description

IV.1.1)Type of procedure

Open procedure

IV.1.3)Information about a framework agreement or a dynamic purchasing system

The procurement involves the establishment of a framework agreement

IV.1.8)Information about the Government Procurement Agreement (GPA)

The procurement is covered by the Government Procurement Agreement: no

IV.2)Administrative information

IV.2.1)Previous publication concerning this procedure

Notice number in the OJ S: [2021/S 231-609058](#)

IV.2.8)Information about termination of dynamic purchasing system

IV.2.9)Information about termination of call for competition in the form of a prior information notice

Section V: Award of contract

Contract No: T005

Title:

Pre-commercial Procurement (PCP) to buy R&D (research and development) services for Breakthrough Solutions for 100% Renewable Energy Supply in Buildings

A contract/lot is awarded: yes

V.2)Award of contract

V.2.1)Date of conclusion of the contract:

10/08/2022

V.2.2)Information about tenders

Number of tenders received: 3

Number of tenders received from SMEs: 2

Number of tenders received from tenderers from other EU Member States: 0

Number of tenders received from tenderers from non-EU Member States: 0

Number of tenders received by electronic means: 3

The contract has been awarded to a group of economic operators: yes

V.2.3)Name and address of the contractor

Official name: R2M Solution Spain SL

Town: Madrid

NUTS code: ES3 Comunidad de Madrid

Country: Spain

The contractor is an SME: yes

V.2.3)Name and address of the contractor

Official name: R2M Solution SRL

Town: Pavia

NUTS code: ITC48 Pavia

Country: Italy

The contractor is an SME: yes

V.2.3)Name and address of the contractor

Official name: Prosume SRL

Town: Milan

NUTS code: ITC4C Milano

Country: Italy

The contractor is an SME: yes

V.2.3)Name and address of the contractor

Official name: Endef Engineering SL

Town: Zaragoza

NUTS code: ES243 Zaragoza

Country: Spain

The contractor is an SME: yes

V.2.3)Name and address of the contractor

Official name: Aire Limpio 2000 SL

Town: Madrid

NUTS code: ES3 Comunidad de Madrid

Country: Spain

The contractor is an SME: yes

V.2.4)Information on value of the contract/lot (excluding VAT)

Total value of the contract/lot: 1 414 752.00 EUR

V.2.5)Information about subcontracting

Section V: Award of contract

Contract No: T001

Title:

CLARITY

A contract/lot is awarded: yes

V.2)Award of contract

V.2.1)Date of conclusion of the contract:

10/08/2022

V.2.2)Information about tenders

Number of tenders received: 3

Number of tenders received from SMEs: 2

Number of tenders received from tenderers from other EU Member States: 3

Number of tenders received from tenderers from non-EU Member States: 0

Number of tenders received by electronic means: 0

The contract has been awarded to a group of economic operators: yes

V.2.3)Name and address of the contractor

Official name: Sener Ingeniería y Sistemas S.A

Town: Getxo

NUTS code: ES213 Bizkaia

Country: Spain

The contractor is an SME: no

V.2.3)Name and address of the contractor

Official name: FUNDACIO EUROCAT

Town: Barcelona

NUTS code: ES511 Barcelona

Country: Spain

The contractor is an SME: no

V.2.4)Information on value of the contract/lot (excluding VAT)

Total value of the contract/lot: 1 414 752.00 EUR

V.2.5)Information about subcontracting

Section V: Award of contract

Contract No: T002

Title:

SEBR

A contract/lot is awarded: yes

V.2)Award of contract

V.2.1)Date of conclusion of the contract:

10/08/2022

V.2.2)Information about tenders

Number of tenders received: 3

Number of tenders received from SMEs: 2

Number of tenders received from tenderers from other EU Member States: 3

Number of tenders received from tenderers from non-EU Member States: 0

Number of tenders received by electronic means: 0

The contract has been awarded to a group of economic operators: yes

V.2.3)Name and address of the contractor

Official name: Defcon8 Enterprise

Town: Barcelona

NUTS code: ES511 Barcelona

Country: Spain

The contractor is an SME: yes

V.2.3)Name and address of the contractor

Official name: Lancey Energy Storage

Town: Grenoble

NUTS code: FRK Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes

Country: France

The contractor is an SME: yes

V.2.3)Name and address of the contractor

Official name: ITEC

Town: Barcelona

NUTS code: ES511 Barcelona

Country: Spain

The contractor is an SME: no

V.2.3)Name and address of the contractor

Official name: Mondas

Town: Freiburg

NUTS code: DE131 Freiburg im Breisgau, Stadtkreis

Country: Germany

The contractor is an SME: yes

V.2.3)Name and address of the contractor

Official name: CIFE

Town: Nice

NUTS code: FRL Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur

Country: France

The contractor is an SME: yes

V.2.3)Name and address of the contractor

Official name: 3OC

Town: Paris

NUTS code: FR101 Paris

Country: France

The contractor is an SME: yes

V.2.4)Information on value of the contract/lot (excluding VAT)

Total value of the contract/lot: 1 414 752.00 EUR

V.2.5)Information about subcontracting

Section VI: Complementary information

VI.3)Additional information:

The PCP procurement is exempted from the WTO Government Procurement Agreement (GPA), the EU public procurement directives and the national laws that implement them (because it concerns the procurement of R&D services where the benefits do not accrue exclusively to the contracting authority for its use in the conduct of its own affairs).

VI.4)Procedures for review

VI.4.1)Review body

Official name: DRŽAVNA REVIZIJSKA KOMISIJA ZA REVIZIJO POSTOPKOV ODDAJE JAVNIH NAROČIL

Postal address: Slovenska cesta 54

Town: Ljubljana

Postal code: 1000

Country: Slovenia

Internet address: <https://portalerevizija.si/>

VI.4.3)Review procedure

Precise information on deadline(s) for review procedures:

Precise information on deadline(s) for review procedures:

Decisions taken with regard to the selection of Suppliers, awarding them with Phases 1, 2 or 3 or excluding them from the procuRE PCP Procedure can be challenged by means of an administrative remedy within a period of 10 days upon the formal notification of the decision. A decision dismissing the appeal could be challenged before the District Court of Velenje. Any dispute or claim arising out of or in connection with the execution of the framework agreement or of the phases contracts entered into between the buyers group and the supplier shall be heard by the District Court of Velenje.

VI.5)Date of dispatch of this notice:

24/08/2022